

NOTES

207, 189, 136, 135, 109, 107° indicated it to be taraxasterol¹⁰. Final confirmation was received by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR spectra) of II, III and IV with the corresponding authentic samples⁹.

Characterisation of A and II admitted compound I as taraxasteryl palmitate [urs-20(30)en-3 β -ol hexadecanoate]. A thorough literature survey indicated that this is the second report of the natural occurrence of taraxasteryl palmitate which was earlier reported¹¹ only recently.

Light petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) eluate fractions of the main chromatogram, after evaporation, afforded a gummy residue which upon repeated chromatography over silica gel furnished a fatty alcohol, crystallised from light petroleum as a micro-crystalline solid, m.p. 84-86° (yield 0.02%) and a triterpene crystallising from light petroleum-benzene mixture (1 : 1) as colourless needles, m.p. 218-19° (yield 0.01%) characterised as taraxasterol (II) by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC, superimposable IR spectra with an authentic sample).

Evaporation of the benzene eluate fractions of the main chromatogram yielded a gummy residue which upon purification through repeated chromatography afforded a sterol (yield 0.02%) crystallising from light petroleum as colourless needles, m.p. 160-61°. This was found to be identical with stigmasterol by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC, IR).

The liquid *L* (R_f 0.7, silica gel G, light petroleum) with a maximum impurity of 2% as shown in the GLC analysis showed positive TNM colouration. ν_{\max} (KBr) 2950 cm^{-1} , 2880 (C-H), 1635 (C=C) indicated it to be an unsaturated hydrocarbon; comparatively strong absorption band at 1375 cm^{-1} is assignable to a large number of methyl substituents⁷. Further study on compound *L* and the fatty alcohol, m.p. 84-86° are in progress.

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Pd(II) Complexes of N,N'-Substituted Thioureas

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Pd(II) complexes of some N-aryl, N'-2(5-halo pyridyl) thioureas were prepared. IR studies reveal that the complexes formed have 1 : 2 metal to ligand ratio. The metal is linked to the ligands through sulphur of thiocarbonyl group.

Experimental

All reagents used were either of B. D. H. or S. MERK Analar grade. The complexes were prepared by adding 0.01M soln. of PdCl₂ (in butanol) slowly and with constant stirring to a hot solution (0.25M) of N-Phenyl, N'-2-(5-Chloro-pyridyl) thiourea, (PCT); N-Phenyl N'-2-(5-Bromo-pyridyl) thiourea, (PBT); N-phenyl, N'-2-(5-Iodo-pyridyl) thiourea, (PIT); N-O-tolyl-2-5(-Chloro-pyridyl) thiourea, (TCT); or N-O-tolyl, N'-2-(5-Bromo-pyridyl) thiourea, (TBT); or N-O-tolyl, N'-2-(5-Iodo-pyridyl) thiourea (TIT) in butanol. The complex got precipitated immediately. It was filtered, washed with butanol and then dried in an air at 60-70°.

The composition of complexes was determined by estimation of the elements N, S, Cl and Pd by standard methods. Conductance measurements were made on a conductivity meter, type LBR, WTW, Germany, using a dip type cell. IR in KBr were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Grating IR Spectrophotometer (Model 237-8).

Results and Discussion

The complexes of PCT, PBT and TCT were reddish in colour whereas that of PIT and PBT were light yellow. They were found soluble in CHCl₃ and CCl₄ but were insoluble in ethanol, butanol, water and ether.

The composition of these complexes on the basis of elemental analysis, could be represented by the general formula PdCl₂L₂, where L is the appropriate substituted thiourea.

The molar conductance of these complexes in chloroform are found to be quite low (3.2-8.2) showing thereby the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. This suggests that chlorine atoms are coordinated to the metal ion and are not present in the ionic form.

The bonds occurring at 1600, 1430 and 1060 cm^{-1} , in the IR spectra of the metal complexes were discussed by earlier workers¹⁻⁵ to decide the donor atoms of the substituted thiourea. The bands appearing at 1600 cm^{-1} was assigned to ($\text{C}=\text{C}+\text{C}=\text{N}$). Except in two cases this band remains almost constant and thus enables the ruling out of the possibility of metal ligand co-ordination through nitrogen or pyridine ring.

The sulphur of substituted thioureas has been found to be one of the co-ordination sites by various workers in this field¹⁻⁶. Yamaguchi et al⁴ were of the opinion that the band assigned to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{N}+\text{C}=\text{S})$ was more important in the diagnosis of metal-sulphur bond where as Swaminathan et al⁵ have given more importance to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ band. But the latter band occurs in the region where many other bands of thiourea are also found and hence its detection is associated with quite some difficulty. Banerji et al² have observed that these bands show shifts to lower frequencies and/or reduce in intensity in the case of metal complexes of N-N' bis (pyridyl) thiourea. Similar observations (lowering of intensity) have been made in the present case too. Moreover, it is found that the intensity of bands is reduced to such an extent, in some of the cases, that the band either disappears completely or its detection is very difficult. In one case these bands are found to be shifted to even higher frequency with lower intensity. Generally on complexation the ligand stretching frequencies are shifted to lower regions due to a decrease in the band order and consequently the force constant. But in some cases, i.e. in nitrile complexes, the $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequencies⁷ and in biuret-metal complexes the N-H stretching frequencies⁸ are found to be increased. This suggests the possibility of metal-ligand co-ordination through sulphur of thiocarbonyl group.

Differences in the position and intensity of metal sulphur bands $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{N}+\text{C}=\text{S})$ in different substituted thiourea complexes may be due to *p*-halo substitution in the pyridyl ring. The electron donating ability of the *p*-halo substituents is in the order $\text{I} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl}$. The electron from the halo-substituents are donated to the pyridine ring, from where these are delocalized with the thiocarbonyl group. As the electron density in the ground level is increased lesser energy is required for excitation and hence the position of band is shifted to longer wavelengths. The intensity of the transition band, which is related to the probability of the transition is also increased for the same reason. The irregularity observed in present case

precludes unambiguous confirmation of his hypothesis.

On the basis of foregoing discussion it is clearly seen that the substituted thioureas studied form 1 : 2 complexes with PdCl_2 in which the thioureas are linked through sulphur to metal and the chlorine atoms remained attached to the metal.

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Syntheses of Copper(II) Complexes with Some new Tridentate Dibasic Schiff Bases

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TRIDENTATE dibasic Schiff bases are novel in the sense that they force the metal (II and III) ions to dimerise or polymerise and as a result metal complexes with unusual magnetic and structural properties are formed^{1,2}. There has been considerable interest on the syntheses and magnetic properties of copper (II) complexes of ONO donor tridentate dibasic Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminophenol³. In this preliminary communication we report the syntheses of several new copper (II) complexes with the ligands

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